

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR CONTENT

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Abstract. *The transition from normative education to innovative education raises the problem of readiness of teachers and teachers to accept new social positions in democratizing relations with students, shifting from reproductive educational tasks to productive and creative mental activity.*

The article talks about innovative technologies and their essence, the uniqueness of innovations in education, the object of influence of innovation and the subjects of activity.

Keywords: *education, creativity, technology, object, activity, innovation, innovation, research, practice.*

Introduction

The system of ideas, theories, rules, forms, methods and tools for improving the pedagogical system and achieving high quality and efficiency can be considered as pedagogical innovations. In recent years, many innovations have been introduced into the pedagogical system. Examples include new concepts, investments, DTS, tests, alternative curricula, new types of schools, technologies, and the like.

The dynamic characteristics of innovation depend on completeness and efficiency, which in turn determines how successful all stages of the innovation process are. What is important here is the transition from simple to extended production. In practice, this transition is often not carried out, which, in turn, leads to the incompleteness of relevant innovations and the existence of many innovation problems.

The efficiency of innovation, unlike completeness (despite their clear relationship), includes the effect of the already realized potential of innovation on various parameters of the system in which the innovation process is carried out.

One of the main concepts discussed in innovative pedagogy is the concept of "new". In a broad sense, "Innovation" envisages the optimization of the educational process, improving its quality and efficiency by introducing innovations into the pedagogical system. Innovation introduced into the pedagogic system can also have a negative impact on quality and efficiency. We understand that innovations are introduced to the system with the aim of increasing quality and efficiency, taking into account its internal reserves and capabilities.

Innovation is "new - something first created or made, appearing or recently made, replacing the previous one, newly discovered, belonging to the recent past or the present, insufficiently familiar, little known" [5].

If the first definition - "first created" - gives an idea of something that was completely unknown before, then the following features - "recently" and especially "rediscovered" - tell us that an element of something already existing "old" can be somewhat new.

Thus, we can talk about two types of new:

1. New (brand new) created for the first time.

Such innovation is equivalent to a discovery in the field of pedagogy.

2. New containing elements of the old.

When old and new elements come together, they can provide a radically new state of knowledge, such as clarification and addition.

Method

Any innovation in education is relative both from a personal and temporal (historical) point of view. What is new to one teacher may not be new to another. Innovation always has a specific historical character, it is born in a specific period and solves the problems of a specific historical period. An innovation can very quickly become the property of many, enter the practice of mass education, but then it can become obsolete and hinder further development.

It is precisely because of the ambiguity of the term "new" (especially in the field of education) that new publications on this issue constantly appear in the pedagogical literature [7]. Let's look at some of them.

According to V. I. Zagvyazinsky, innovation in pedagogy is not only ideas, approaches, methods and technologies that have not been used before, but also a set of elements (or individual elements of the pedagogical process) with a progressive beginning that allows effective solving of educational problems in changing conditions and situations [4]. That is, in the interpretation of this author, innovation actually corresponds to the concept of "progressiveness". However, in practice, it is known that innovation does not always correspond to progressiveness and development, even the broader concept of "modernity".

N.R. Yusufbekova, a researcher of the problems of pedagogical innovation, defines innovation as the content of changes in the pedagogical reality that were previously unknown and did not yet lead to results, which can develop the theory and practice of education. This content can refer to the entire pedagogical reality and its separate components.

Considering the system of basic concepts of pedagogical innovation, N.R. Yusufbekova (131) distinguishes three structural blocks of innovative processes in the educational system:

The first block is the block of creating new things in pedagogy. Categories such as innovations in pedagogy, classification of educational innovations, conditions for creation of new ones, criteria of innovation, measure of readiness to master and use new ones, traditions and innovations, stages of creation of new ones in pedagogy are considered here.

The second block is the block of new perception, assimilation and evaluation. In this block, concepts such as pedagogical team, evaluation of innovations, innovation environment, readiness of the pedagogical team to perceive and evaluate new things are presented.

The third block is the new use and application block. In this block, the rules and types of introduction, use and application of the new are studied.

Due to the different interpretations of the term "new" in the field of education, until now there is no generally accepted interpretation of the concept of "educational innovation" in the pedagogical literature and in the innovative educational environment.

Many scientists (similar to N.R. Yusufbekova's research, which identified three blocks in the composition of any innovation in the field of education) give a broader understanding of educational innovation, understanding it as a process of creating, mastering, using and distributing new things. Some researchers dealing with this issue give a more strict definition of educational innovation, by which they understand only the activity of creating new things. The processes of assimilation, use, distribution of the new are not considered by them to be truly innovative.

Results and discussion

In the collaborative monograph "innovative movement in school education" [9] of scientists and practitioners dealing with innovation problems, the real difficulties behind various cases and the corresponding interpretations of the concept of "educational innovation" are analyzed.

The first case is the case of some educational leaders who tend to continuously increase the number of educational innovations according to the work situation. According to them, any change in the school is an innovation. Undoubtedly, such an approach can threaten to devalue all innovative activities in the educational system.

The second case is methodological - technocratic. Some methodologists directly and sometimes mechanically transfer the general concepts of innovation to the field of education and look at education itself only through the general methodological or production-technical prism of innovations, or only from the point of view of economic use of educational innovations. Through such views, important features of education are lost.

The uniqueness of educational innovation, for example, while retaining all the common features of innovative processes, educational innovation differs from similar processes in other fields, because the object of influence of innovation and the subject of activity are related to the personality of the teacher and the teacher.

If this is ignored, educational innovations related to the child and the teacher themselves will be reduced from all humanitarian, humane components of innovative activity, in particular, towards the formation of innovative consciousness of teaching.

The third case is part of the innovative elite. In recent times, representatives of this situation often try to distinguish the innovative movement from the movement called "school renewal" by a too strict understanding of educational innovation. This division and opposition of the two movements is quite correct and, in our opinion, based on a false alternative.

In fact, such a strict approach can "narrow" the general idea and reduce the entire process of innovative education to the study of only individual (albeit important) elements. Thus, systematic views of pedagogical problems disappear, and the class of innovative tasks in the field of education narrows.

Therefore, such a statement of the problem and the possibility of different interpretations of the concept of "educational innovation" impose on any researcher who starts to deal with this problem, first of all, to make a conscious and reasonable choice about the understanding of innovation, and then to research this working concept.

Innovations in the educational system are:

- purpose, content, method, technology, form of organization and management system;
- to organize the originality of the pedagogical activity and the learning process;
- to the system of control and assessment of educational levels;
- educational and methodological support;
- system of educational work;
- curriculum and educational programs;
- depends on the activity of the student and the teacher.

The aim is to obtain the highest possible result from the spent money and effort in the application of innovations in the educational system or educational activities. Innovation differs

from any innovation in that it must have a changeable mechanism that allows for management and control.

In education, as in all fields, there is talk about "innovation", "innovation" and activities that represent their essence.

In the scientific literature, special attention is paid to the difference between the concepts of "novation" (updating, innovation) and "innovation" (introducing something new). For example, according to V. I. Zagvyazinsky, the concept of "new", "innovation" represents not only a specific idea, but also an approach, method and technologies that have not yet been used in practice. But in this case, the elements of the process consist of whole or separate elements, and reflect the ideas of effectively solving the tasks of education and upbringing in changing conditions and situations. In fact, innovation is considered a tool, and in most cases it manifests itself in the form of a new method, methodology, technology, etc. In essence, there are certain differences between novation and innovation. They are as follows (Table 1):

Table 1

Key differences between novation and innovation

The main differences	
Novation	Innovation
1) is used based on the current theory; 2) scope is limited by time; 3) methods are updated; 4) the result improves the previous system	1) will be systematic, integrated and continuous; 2) designs a new activity system in a given practice; 3) the activities of the entities are fully updated; 4) new technologies are created; 5) new qualitative results are achieved in the activity; 6) the practice itself is updated

Innovative indicators in the field of education are the presence of one or more of the following directions:

- close relationship with higher education institutions;
- in-depth study of humanitarian sciences;
- in-depth study of natural sciences;
- innovative methods, developmental education;
- computer skills and knowledge;
- lyceum system;
- orientation to mathematics;
- unique methods of education and training;
- "Kindergarten - primary school - secondary school - higher education institution" system;
- the concept of restoration of traditions, national culture;
- artistic, musical, aesthetic education;
- economic direction;
- language specialization.

It can be seen that in the form of innovative technologies, phenomena related to the reconstruction or change of the improvement of individual aspects and features of the system, and which do not change the foundations of the organization of modern education as a whole, occupy a large place.

The basis of implementation of the innovative, creative nature of teaching is a new type of social relations between the older and the younger generation, between the teacher and the students. These are democratic relationships that involve mutual aid, coordination, cooperation, and co-creation.

Summary

In the framework of innovative education, conditions are created for the development of a person, his individual creative contribution, personal initiative, and the right to freedom of self-development are realized.

There are different models of innovative education in modern psychology and pedagogy, but the main feature of the innovative strategy in the educational process is personality development. The basis of such models is the principle of joint creative activity of the teacher and students, which is implemented according to two conditions of development: a) activity of the student; b) his cooperation with the teacher. Education is carried out by solving creative problems related to increasing readiness for the future, forming expectations.

Therefore, innovations are fundamentally new forms of activity that allow to achieve a high level of quality. Innovation in the field of education, if it is a holistic theoretical, technological concept of renewal, is the basis for the development of a creative, healthy, highly educated person.

The transition from normative education to innovative education requires the democratization of the relationship between teachers and students, the abandonment of the strict union of the social roles of "teacher - student" in educational conditions, the transfer of new social positions of cooperation (from authoritarian management - to cooperative activity; from reproductive educational tasks - to effective and creative mental activity). increases the problem of readiness to accept. Even if the creative ability and professional skills of the teacher are high, it is a difficult task to change the personal attitude, master the methods of democratization of relations and communication with students. Creative thinking, cooperation, culture of communication and culture of activity, self-awareness and the need for student's self-awareness, professional competence - this is the basis of a teacher's professional activity in an innovative school. All this means that in the innovative transformation of education, it is necessary to create an innovative educational space in which the tasks of the educational process are solved comprehensively based on the principles of mutual enrichment, mutual respect, cooperation of teachers, students, parents, and the administration. It is also important to consider and distinguish specific educational content that engages children in the practice of personal self-management (managing their feelings, intuition, communication, behavior, and ways of projecting their "I").

In addition, development of innovative educational technologies, reform of goals and strategies, analysis and evaluation of introduced innovations, creation of conditions for their development and application are among the urgent tasks of today.

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